

Iron(II)-catalysed Debromination of *vic*-Dibromides in *N,N*-Dimethylformamide

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DEBROMINATION of *vic*-dibromides stereospecifically and stereoselectively, to give olefins, has been studied widely¹. Attempts have been made to optimise a number of different reaction conditions involving a variety of reducing agents including metal ions², the most common being zinc, magnesium and halide ions. *meso*-Stilbene dibromide has invariably been chosen as a model substrate.

We undertook the study of debromination to evolve a simple procedure using iron(II) ions and report here a novel method of debromination using a very simple workup. The debromination could be achieved quantitatively by heating the substrate with iron(II) oxalate in dry dimethylformamide at 100° for ~2 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc. Addition of reaction mixture to dilute H₂SO₄ gave the products which were filtered, dried and characterised (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DEBROMINATION OF *vic*-DIBROMIDES WITH IRON(II) OXALATE IN 1 : 1 MOLAR RATIO IN DMF AT 100°

Halide	Time min	Isolated yield* %
<i>meso</i> -Benzalacetophenone dibromide	75	95
<i>meso</i> -Stilbene dibromide	75	96 ^a
<i>meso</i> -Cinnamic acid dibromide	75	98
<i>meso</i> - <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzalacetophenone dibromide	100	91
<i>meso</i> -Methyl cinnamate dibromide	120	98 ^b
<i>meso</i> -Benzalacetone dibromide	120	92 ^b
<i>trans</i> -1,2-Dibromocyclohexane	180	22 ^c

*Glc analyses showed only *E*-stilbene and no *Z*-stilbene, ^bproduct isolated by extraction with solvent ether as being a low melting solid, ^cHplc analyses showed the presence of cyclohexene (22%) and starting material (78%) after 180 min of refluxing at 150°.

The reaction was very slow at 80° and no debromination was observed in tetrahydrofuran, 1,4-dioxane and acetonitrile as solvents. The debromination could also be achieved by other iron(II) salts. The reaction is best suited for aromatic substrates as debromination of *trans*-1,2-dibromocyclohexane was only 22% complete even after refluxing at 150° for 3 h as monitored by hplc.

Experimental

The products were identified by their m.p., m.m.p. and comparison of ir and nmr spectra with

those of the authentic samples. All the m.ps. were recorded on Tropical Labequip apparatus.

The *vic*-dibromides were prepared by the reported methods. Iron(II) oxalate (Veb Laborchemie Apolda, Germany) was used. Dimethylformamide (B.D.H. and Merck) was used in all reactions after drying.

General procedure : A mixture of the *vic*-dibromide (0.01 mol), iron oxalate (0.01 mol) and dry dimethylformamide was flushed with N₂ gas for 15 min and heated in an oil-bath at 100°. The progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc. After complete debromination, the contents of the flask were poured in 1N H₂SO₄ (200 ml). The mixture was stirred for 5 min and resulting solid was filtered, dried in air, and recrystallised.

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Synthesis of some New Halogenohydroxymethyl Flavones

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CONSIDERING the therapeutic and synthetic importance of chromones¹, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise some new flavones and evaluate their antifungal activity.

The synthesis of the chromones (2) was carried out from the chalcones (1) by oxidative cyclisation using selenium dioxide in isoamyl alcohol. The starting materials 1-(2'-hydroxy-3'/5'-chloro-5'/3'-hydroxymethylphenyl)-3-aryl-2-propen-1-ones (1) were prepared by condensing 2-hydroxy-3/5-chloro-5/3-hydroxymethylacetophenones² with various substituted aromatic aldehydes in presence of alcoholic KOH. In all the flavones, the lowering

NOTES

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2a AND 2b*

Sl. no.	R''	M.p.** °C	Yield %	ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)			
				C=O	O=C	Pyrone	Alcoholic OH stretch (bend)
2a (R=CH₂OH ; R'=Cl)							
1.	Phenyl	170 ^a	70	1 644	1 560	1 330	1 032 (2 918)
2.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	139 ^a	70	1 633	1 545	1 327	1 025 (2 910)
3.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	191 ^a	80	1 630	1 540	1 325	1 025 (2 908)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	190 ^a	75	1 648	1 565	1 345	1 035 (2 925)
5.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	177 ^a	70	1 632	1 545	1 320	1 031 (2 916)
6.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	201 ^a	70	1 649	1 570	1 325	1 038 (2 920)
7.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	221 ^a	72	1 645	1 565	1 350	1 036 (2 914)
8.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	231 ^a	75	1 643	1 562	1 320	1 034 (2 912)
9.	α -Naphthyl	200 ^b	65	1 642	1 554	1 325	1 030 (2 918)
10.	β -Methoxynaphthyl	218 ^b	60	1 638	1 550	1 321	1 028 (2 911)
2b (R=Cl, R'=CH₂OH)							
11.	Phenyl	158 ^a	70	1 642	1 555	1 325	1 027 (2 917)
12.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	131 ^a	72	1 630	1 550	1 322	1 025 (2 910)
13.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	179 ^a	75	1 631	1 549	1 320	1 031 (2 912)
14.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	131 ^a	70	1 645	1 552	1 330	1 033 (2 928)
15.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	168 ^a	72	1 642	1 548	1 325	1 027 (2 915)
16.	α -Naphthyl	198 ^a	70	1 635	1 545	1 345	1 029 (2 927)

*Analysis of Cl found satisfactory. **Solvent for crystallisation : ^aEtOH, ^bAcOH.

of normal carbonyl stretching frequency in ir spectra is attributable to conjugated nature³ of the ketones and contribution in ionic character⁴.

a, R=CH₂OH, R'=Cl
 b, R=Cl, R'=CH₂OH
 R''=Ph, *o*-, *p*-Cl, *o*-Me,
p-OMe, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-OH-phenyl,
 α - β -OMe-naphthyl

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin - Elmer Infracord 237 spectrophotometer.

General methods for synthesis of 2-aryl-6/8-chloro-8/6-hydroxymethylchromones : A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and selenium dioxide (0.01 mol) in isoamyl alcohol (20 ml) was refluxed for 10 - 12 h. Isoamyl alcohol was then removed from the filtrate by steam distillation and the non-volatile residue was extracted with benzene. The benzene layer was washed with aqueous sodium carbonate (10%) and water, and the solvent evaporated to afford the flavones (Table 1).

Biological activity : Some of the representative compounds of 2a and 2b series were tested against *Penicillium notatum*, and none of them was found to be active.

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Synthesis and Spectroscopic Studies of some 2-Amino-3-cyano-4,6-disubstituted- pyridines

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CYANOPYRIDINES exhibit various biological activities^{1,2}. During the last few years only a few cyanopyridine derivatives have been synthesised by Michael reaction³ and by other methods⁴. In view of the biological activity of cyanopyridines, we

have synthesised a number of new 2-amino-3-cyano-4,6-disubstituted-pyridines, characterised by elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectral studies.

Experimental

The chalcones have been synthesised according to the reported method⁴. Melting points are uncorrected.

2-Amino-3-cyano-4,6-disubstituted-pyridines: A mixture of chalcone (1 mol), dicyanomethane (1 mol) and ammonium acetate (8 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (150 ml) for 8–10 h on a water-bath. The cooled contents were then poured in ice with constant stirring to obtain a solid yellow mass, washed with water and rectified spirit, and the residue was crystallised by using a mixture of DMF and ethanol (Table 1).

Carbon and hydrogen were analysed by a Coleman 5602 analyser. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl₃; TMS as internal standard) on a Perkin-Elmer RB-12 spectrometer.

Results and Discussion

The condensation of acetophenones (1 mol) with benzaldehydes (1 mol) in presence of sodium hydroxide and ethanol yielded chalcones (1). The chalcones and dicyanomethane reacted in 1:1 molar ratio in presence of ammonium acetate to give 2-amino-3-cyano-4,6-disubstituted-pyridines (2) through Michael reaction with the elimination of water (1 mol each) and hydrogen (Scheme 1). All the cyanopyridines (2) are yellow coloured high melting solids, and soluble in CHCl₃, DMSO and TFA. 2 showed three ir bands at 3 140–3 480 cm⁻¹ (NH₂) and a strong band at 2 220 cm⁻¹ (C≡N); nmr spectra showed the resonances of aromatic ≡CH

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE CYANOPYRIDINES (2)

Sl. no.	R	R ¹	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Analyses % : Found/(Calcd.)	
						C	H
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₃	176	88	80.10 (79.70)	5.10 (4.80)
2.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -OH ₂ .C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃	160	94	80.20 (80.00)	5.27 (5.26)
3.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -OOC ₂ .C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O	170	36	75.55 (75.75)	4.70 (4.98)
4.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ BrN ₃	187	28	61.92 (61.71)	3.70 (3.48)
5.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ ClN ₃	212	30	71.00 (70.70)	3.78 (3.98)
6.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃	203–05	28	68.85 (68.85)	3.50 (3.80)
7.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ ClN ₃	170–72	38	70.30 (70.70)	3.64 (3.98)
8.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₃	200	30	63.88 (63.58)	3.54 (3.24)
9.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ ClO ₂ N ₃	230–32	50	61.90 (61.68)	3.31 (3.14)